

Immune Mediated Hemolytic Anemia - An Overview

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Introduction

Immune Mediated Hemolytic Anemia (IMHA) is a complex disease characterized by immune destruction of red blood cells that have been coated with immunoglobulins, complement or both, resulting in destruction of erythrocytes either extravascularly or intravascularly. Antibodies may be directed against normal erythrocytes (primary or idiopathic) or against erythrocytes that have been antigenically altered through interaction with secondary causes viz., drugs, neoplasia and infectious diseases.

IMHA is one of the most common causes of anemia in small animals but less common in ruminants, horses and other large animals.

IMHA represents a type II hypersensitivity reaction which involves formation of anti-erythrocytic antibodies which get fixed on the erythrocyte surface leads to destruction of erythrocytes. Anti-erythrocytic antibodies including IgG, IgM, and IgA attach directly or indirectly to various components of the erythrocytic membrane viz., Glycophorin, Band 3 etc.

Types of IMHA

IMHA can be classified into primary and secondary based on presence of underlying cause of erythrocyte destruction. It is an important classification in clinical point of view. Primary (idiopathic) IMHA is a classic example of an autoimmune disorder with no identifiable underlying cause and is the predominant form of IMHA. Normally, auto antibodies are prevented from reacting with host tissues by suppressor T cells. It is believed that, IMHA-affected animals have poorly regulated suppressor T-cell function or over stimulated immune systems that allow auto antibodies to attach to normal cells and trigger RBC destruction. In primary IMHA, there is no evidence of recent drug or vaccine administration

and the antibody is considered to be a true autoantibody with specificity for a self - antigen of the RBC membrane.

Secondary IMHA is caused by an immunologic response to non-self-antigens that have modified or are associated with normal RBC membranes. Secondary IMHA can be caused by a number of underlying processes. Affected RBCs may become infected by pathogens or coated with foreign antigen. Documented or hypothesized causes of secondary IMHA include bacterial, viral, rickettsial, parasitic, protozoan, and neoplastic disorders.

Clinical Manifestations Of IMHA

Clinical signs seen in IMHA patients often include those associated with anemia and tissue hypoxia which includes lethargy, weakness, and tachypnea. Clinical examination may reveal Pale mucous membranes, Tachycardia, bounding pulses and less commonly Splenomegaly, hepatomegaly, lymph node enlargement can be found. Other findings may include, Hemic murmur, jaundice if there is acute severe hemolysis, Hemoglobinuria (“port wine” urine) Petechiae, ecchymoses, and melena in patients with concurrent immune-mediated thrombocytopenia.

Diagnostic Tests for IMHA

Complete blood count and blood smear examination

Complete blood count reveals normocytic and normochromic anemia includes low hematocrit and erythrocyte count. Leukocytosis with neutrophilia represents the altered bone marrow reactivity as a result of inflammatory mediator’s influence. Blood smear examination reveal Auto agglutination, Spherocytes, Polychromasia, Anisocytosis, Poikilocytosis, Reticulocytotic, presence of nucleated RBCs.

Serum chemistry profile

Abnormalities in the serum chemistry profile may reflect organ damage from hypoxia or indicate an underlying disease process. Hyperbilirubinemia is common in IMHA. Hyperbilirubinemia as a result of intense bilirubin metabolism. Increased liver transaminases due to hepatocyte hypoxic damage and hyperproteinemia because of hyperglobulinemia.

Slide agglutination test

Slide agglutination test is useful tool in diagnosing IMHA. Persistent agglutination indicative of IMHA. The slide agglutination test can be easily performed in practice, and is used to differentiate true autoagglutination from rouleaux formation (nonimmune RBC adhesion). Mix a drop of physiologic saline to drop of anticoagulated blood onto a clean, dry glass slide and inspect for microagglutination. If clumping is observed, it may be either due to auto agglutination or due to rouleaux formation. Add

more drops of saline, if agglutination persists or clumping is observed it indicates autoagglutination because rouleaux formation is dispersed after adding more drops of saline.

Coagulation profile

Coagulation tests, such as the prothrombin time (PT) or activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), are indicated to assess for hemostatic disorders, such as Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), Thromboembolic disease. Possible alterations are prolonged prothrombin time, prolonged partial thromboplastin time, low fibrinogen level, positive D-dimer test. They indicate an impaired hemocoagulation and a prothrombotic tendency. Prolonged coagulation times have not been shown to predict thromboembolism or mortality in patients with IMHA. However, the presence of DIC may indicate a more severe case of IMHA.

Coomb's test (Direct agglutination test) (DAT)

Specific immunological testing can be used to support a tentative diagnosis of IMHA. The goal of the immunological assays is to determine the presence of antierythrocyte antibodies fixed on RBCs surface. A specific immunological assay for the detection of antierythrocyte antibodies is the direct antiglobulin test (Coombs'test). A suspension of washed patient RBCs with membrane immunoglobulin or complement attached in vivo, is incubated with an antiglobulin reagent that cross - links these immunoreactants, forming a lattice that appears grossly as an agglutinate of RBCs.

Conclusions

IMHA is complex disease in which hemolysis occurs because of anti-erythrocyte antibody production. IMHA is most commonly recognised in Dog, cat, horse and cattle. In Primary IMHA there is no identifiable underlying cause while secondary IMHA caused by variety of infectious agents, Drugs or neoplastic disorders. Low hematocrit value, regenerative anemia, spherocytosis and persistent agglutination are the hallmark of IMHA. Coomb's test is used for confirmatory diagnosis of IMHA.